

The Intrinsic Response of Several Single-Fiber SiC/Ti-6Al-4V Composites to Transverse Tension

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ABSTRACT

The fiber-matrix debond stress in transversely-loaded SiC fiber/Ti matrix composites has traditionally been estimated by observing the interface at the free surface under load. Recent evidence suggests that observations of the free surface, however, may lead to an underestimate of the debond stress due to the presence of debonding and stress concentrations. In the present work, a cross-shaped specimen design is proposed to eliminate the influence of the free surface, thereby providing a more realistic measurement of the transverse load-carrying capability of the fiber/matrix interface. This test has been successfully used to monitor interface debonding in SiC fiber/titanium alloy composites using fibers with different interface coatings, and therefore different bonding characteristics.

INTRODUCTION

Studies of the load-carrying capability (LCC) of continuous-fiber titanium matrix composites in the direction normal to the fiber axis (transverse loading) are generally accomplished by testing straight-sided or reduced-section tensile coupons. Typically, the interface at the free surface is observed directly via optical or scanning electron microscope (SEM) observations, or indirectly using edge replication. Only recently have attempts been made at studying the debond event away from the free surface [1-4]. The reason for these latest approaches is that the interface intersecting the free surface is suspected of being debonded in the as-prepared state due to thermal residual stresses [4-6], and the geometric discontinuity at the surface can also be a stress concentration point for applied loads. A debond crack at the free surface may be able to open and also propagate into the bulk of the sample under low applied stresses. Previous approaches may therefore severely underestimate the interface bond strength.

A cross-shaped specimen geometry has been developed to determine the transverse properties of a single-fiber composite [1]. A diagram of the sample is given in Fig. 1. The fiber is contained in the transverse section of the cross (or the "wing" section). The reason for this specimen design is to isolate the free surfaces from the portion of the interface tested in tension, and to therefore force the debond event to occur in the center of the sample. Since the samples are very thin (300-400 μm), a very small strain gauge on the sample surface directly above the fiber can measure an increase of local specimen compliance due to fiber-matrix debonding, matrix plasticity, or fiber breaking. Another advantage of forcing internal crack initiation is possibly a

larger acoustic signal than in the case where an interface crack propagates from the free surface; therefore, in conjunction with the strain gage, acoustic emissions from the sample were also constantly monitored.

Figure 1. Diagram of the cross-shaped specimen used for testing the fiber-matrix interface in transverse tension. The fiber is contained in the transverse portion of the cross (or the "wings").

Composites of SCS-6 fiber/Ti-6Al-4V matrix have been studied using the cross geometry and the debond event has been reported to initiate at an average applied stress of 291 MPa [1]. This result is significantly different from studies of single-fiber composites using straight-sided samples where debonding at the free surface is found at stresses of 100-150 MPa [7]. Studies of full volume fraction SCS-6 composites typically report that the initial nonlinearity, or "knee" in transverse stress-strain curves, which has been associated with fiber-matrix debonding and attendant matrix plasticity, occurs at stresses of 140-250 MPa [8-10]. These values are also slightly less than those measured with the cross samples. Of course, residual stresses, which are expected to be different for all these cases, play an important role in the failure stress of the interface and their effect in the present case is the subject of ongoing research. If, however, the sample geometry is held constant, then the influence of the residual stresses may be similar for all samples and the behavior of SiC fibers with different surfaces can be compared.

The present study will report on an investigation of the LCC of several SiC fiber/Ti-6Al-4V systems. The fibers reported have been fabricated with chemical vapor deposition (CVD) by two manufacturers. The objective was not to compare the results obtained on the basis of the manufacturer, but to compare on the basis of the interfaces present to gain a clearer understanding of the ability of the fiber and interface to carry load.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Composite specimens were prepared by diffusion bonding Ti-6Al-4V matrix foils in a vacuum hot press. The composite panels were then thinned by chemical etching (10% HF, 20% HNO₃, 70% H₂O) from 810 μm to the range of 320-380 μm . Cross-shaped samples were prepared using electron discharge machining (EDM). The dimensions of the cross samples were $2h = 0.318$ cm, $l = 1.90$ cm, $w = 0.635$ cm, and $d = 5.5$ cm (See Fig. 1). Small fillets (0.8 x 0.8 mm) to minimize stress concentrations at the inside corners of the cross, and also end tabs were cut into the samples. The specimens were instrumented with one strain gage (0.8 x 0.8 mm) placed on the sample surface directly above the fiber, and two transducers were placed on the sample to monitor acoustic emissions.

Five different fibers were investigated. The results from SCS-6 have been reported earlier [1], but two other fibers manufactured by Textron Specialty Materials Division (Lowell, MA) were also tested. One was SCS-0 (140 μm diameter), which is a SiC fiber with no surface coating. The second was SCS-6 with only a single SCS layer (1-2 μm) on its surface (single-pass)

instead of the two layers applied to the SCS-6 fiber; this fiber is therefore designated SCS-6 SP. The SCS coating is a carbon-rich layer containing a significant amount of silicon carbide in the form of small crystallites [11-12]. Amercom (Chatsworth, CA) manufactured the other two fibers tested in this study. The first was designated ACMF since the SiC was deposited on a carbon monofilament. According to the manufacturer, the ACMF fiber has only a very thin carbon layer on its surface ($< 0.5 \mu\text{m}$) for improved handleability. The other Amercom fiber is AC1 and has a "hard" carbon coating of approximately $3 \mu\text{m}$ in thickness. The SCS-type fibers all have an approximate diameter of $140 \mu\text{m}$, while that of the Amercom fibers is $127 \mu\text{m}$.

RESULTS

Typical stress-strain curves and the acoustic events for the SCS-6, ACMF, SCS-0, and AC1 fibers are given in Fig. 2a-d. The curve for SCS-6 SP was very similar to that of SCS-6, so only the SCS-6 curve is reported. Four tests of SCS-6, three of ACMF, and two each of the other fibers were completed. The initial modulus of the curves was measured to be in the range of 110-120 GPa which is very close to the Young's modulus of Ti-6Al-4V (113 GPa) as measured in the earlier study [1]. The tests were typically stopped at strain levels (at the fiber cross) of 0.9%.

The interfaces can be ranked in terms of the average stress level required to cause a nonlinearity in the loading curve of the samples. The lowest in terms of this value is AC1 (215 MPa), then SCS-6 SP (260 MPa), SCS-6 (291 MPa), SCS-0 (330 MPa), and ACMF (412 MPa). In some cases the initial nonlinearity was punctuated with a significant jump in strain and in others the change in slope was gradual.

The results for the SCS-6 and SCS-6 SP fiber were similar. Five of the six curves exhibited sudden jumps in strain which marked the beginning of the nonlinearity in the curves. This initial jump was followed by a second jump (typically equal in magnitude), separated by a strain of approximately 0.03 to 0.05%. The lower the strain level where these events occurred, the smaller the magnitude of the jump. After the pair of jumps, the slope of the curve was much lower.

The SCS-6 sample tested in Fig. 2a was sectioned parallel the sample face in order to reveal the fiber in cross section along its length (see Fig. 3) [1]. The interface appears to be different in the central region as opposed to the wing section. The reaction products are clearly evident in the outer wing region (Fig. 3a) and not in the center region, where there appears to be a gap in its place.

Fig. 2b is a plot of stress and strain for a single cross sample of ACMF, and includes acoustic emissions from the sample. The most notable feature of the plot is the large increase in strain that occurs at a strain of 0.49% and a stress of 548 MPa. This event was accompanied by a very high amplitude acoustic emission. Prior to this event, however, there was some nonlinearity in the curve beginning at 0.43% and 461 MPa that was also accompanied by significant acoustic emissions. The large strain increase was followed by a smaller increase at a strain of 0.61% and a stress of 581 MPa. There were significant acoustic emissions just before, during and after this second event.

The sample tested in Fig. 2b was polished to reveal the fiber-matrix interface along the entire fiber length and optical micrographs of portions of the cross-section are given in Fig. 3. At the interface outside of the center section (in the wing), there was no evidence of damage at the interface, however, in the center section a gap was clearly visible. Over much of the center region the gap was along the top interface (as pictured), but it also is present inside the fiber, thereby indicating fiber fracture. The interface directly above and below the fractured fiber had very little or no interface separation.

Two other single-cross ACMF samples were also tested and had slightly different behavior. The first exhibited one major jump in strain (0.025%) at approximately 0.29% and 340 MPa. There were no other sudden increases in strain for this sample. The final ACMF test exhibited no large jumps in strain. The curve does, however, become nonlinear at a stress of 435 MPa and a strain of 0.38%. The average stress where the ACMF curves became nonlinear was 412 MPa.

The results from the two SCS-0 tests were similar to ACMF (Fig. 2c). The curves became nonlinear at an average stress of 330 MPa (0.29%) and the slope gradually decreased until there was a large jump in strain at an average 545 MPa (0.58%). The nonlinearity and jumps were accompanied by a great deal of acoustic emission.

A representative stress-strain curve for a test with the AC1 fiber is given in Fig. 2d. The curve became nonlinear at a strain of only 0.18% and a stress of 210 MPa. Of the fibers tested thus far, this one has exhibited the lowest stress associated with the initial point of nonlinearity in its stress-strain curve.

DISCUSSION

The most general observation that can be drawn from the data presented is that the fiber surface coating has a significant impact on the loading behavior in the cross-specimens. The AC1 fiber showed nonlinearity at much lower loads than the other fibers. The SCS-0 and ACMF fiber composites sustained greater loads until the nonlinearity was observed. The coated SCS-type fibers were intermediate and tended to exhibit a double strain jump in the loading curves.

The sudden increases in strain noticed in many of the plots suggest that significant strain is being accumulated at once in the vicinity of the fiber. Sudden unloading of the fiber by interface and/or fiber failure is expected to cause a jump in strain and the associated reduction in slope following the event. In addition, significant plasticity can cause nonlinearity in the loading curve. The very sudden accumulation of a significant amount of local strain, however, is most probably the result of brittle failure in the material (i.e., interface or fiber failure). Interface failure, and not fiber failure, was found in the case of SCS-6 (Fig. 3b) and interface and fiber failure were found in the case of ACMF (Fig. 3d). Localized plasticity on the sample surface adjacent to the fiber was also observed after the test by observation of a shallow surface indentation on the sample above the fiber [1].

If the jumps in strain for SCS-6 are due to interface failure, then the interface must have some measurable strength. This is contrary to the assumption that the SCS interface is negligibly weak and the knee in the stress-strain curve of high volume fraction composites is due to the applied stress simply overcoming the residual thermal stresses at the interface [9]. If the interface does have significant strength then the applied stress must overcome the residual stresses *and* the interface bond strength. Analyses to determine the strength of the interfacial bond are currently underway.

An important issue is the degree of consolidation of the composites tested. With the present consolidation technique, it is possible to have a gap or pore at the fiber-matrix interface at the pole of the fiber where the external stress is applied. A gap in this position can possibly lead to premature failure of the interface and therefore lower interface strength values. Examination of the fiber in the wings suggests that the two SCS-6 samples that yielded low interface strengths had gaps present in at least one wing. The larger stresses measured for the interface strength in the other two samples may therefore be more indicative of the true strength. Further work is being conducted to ensure complete consolidation and therefore minimize this effect.

The mechanism of interface debonding, whether along a specific bimaterial interface (interlayer) or through one phase at the interface (intra-layer) is of significant interest. Several preliminary observations can be made, but this work is ongoing. In SCS-type fibers the reaction zone became severely cracked during the tests and this obscured the identity of the debonding

interface. It is possible that the fiber coatings failed and this resulted in the interface failure, however, there were no gaps or any evidence of failure between the inner SCS layer and the fiber, or between the two SCS layers. The similar behavior of the SCS-6 and SCS-6 SP fibers also indicates that the bond between the two SCS layers is not the failure location for the interface in this loading condition. Using fiber pushout tests, researchers have found that the SCS-6/titanium interface typically fails between the outer SCS layer and the layer of reaction products (RP) [6,14]. Transverse failure in the case of SCS-6 and SCS-6 SP seems to be consistent with this observation, but may have resulted from separation at the RP-matrix interface or by failure of the reaction products. This same observation was made for AIC fibers. The interface failure mechanism in ACMF and SCS-0 is currently being investigated.

The results from AC1 indicate that the bond strength at the interface is extremely weak. Jumps in strain were not evident when the curve changed slope, and no acoustic emissions were present, but this may be due to the low strain energy in the sample at the time. These very low values of initial nonlinearity in the loading curve also substantiate the claim that the SCS-6 interface has some significant bond strength since the residual stresses (which are not expected to be significantly different for these two cases) at the interface were overcome at such a low stress level in this material.

The nonlinearity in the stress-strain curve of SCS-0 and ACMF before the large jumps in strain are also of interest. It is possible that they are due to matrix plasticity or stable failure of the interface or fiber. The fiber, of course, has a very low fracture toughness ($2.2 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$) [13] and the stable growth of a crack in the fiber is therefore not likely. The interface may, however, have a higher toughness than the fiber due to matrix deformation, and therefore fast fracture may not occur until the crack size and stress levels are sufficient. Matrix yielding in the neighborhood of the fiber may also lead to a significant reduction in the slope of the curve. According to the calculations of Nimmer et al. [9], however, matrix plasticity in the presence of a strong interface bond is not expected until much higher applied stresses are reached ($>1000 \text{ MPa}$) in high (35%) fiber volume fraction material. This suggests that the nonlinearity observed in the curves before the large jumps in stress is due to stable interface failure which may have induced matrix plasticity near the fiber. The initial point of nonlinearity may therefore be an indication of the stress needed to overcome the residual stresses and the interface strength. The reason that the initial nonlinearity took place at much lower strains in SCS-0 than ACMF is not presently known, but may be related to the smaller fiber diameter in the case of ACMF. The thin carbon layer on the ACMF fiber may also play a role in the bonding of the fiber, but kinetics of the fiber-matrix reaction suggest that the C layer will be completely consumed during the fabrication process. In order to further understand the test results, the failure process and matrix plasticity in the presence of residual stresses are currently being modeled using numerical methods.

CONCLUSIONS

The most important conclusion of the present work is that transverse tensile tests using specimens with a cross geometry and instrumented in the manner discussed, measure large differences in the load-carrying ability of the composite depending on the specific fiber surface characteristics chosen. The initial nonlinearity, which may give an indication of the interface "strength," was very low for the pure carbon coated fiber (AC1), higher for SCS-type fibers (SCS-6, and SCS-6 SP), still higher for SCS-0, and highest for ACMF. The latter two have an SiC-rich surface, while the former two have carbon-rich surface coatings. This suggests that SiC bonds more strongly to titanium than does C under the consolidation conditions. Results from well-consolidated panels where fiber fracture does not preclude loading of the interface to failure, and the composite is fully consolidated, also seem to be reproducible. Failure of all of the fibers seemed to occur in the vicinity of the reaction products, and not within the coatings, or at the fiber-coating interface. It is not known whether failure of the reaction products caused interface failure, or if one of the reaction product (fiber-reaction product, or reaction product-matrix) interfaces separated first. The failure of the interfaces in all of the coated fibers seemed to occur between the outer coating layer and the matrix. The specifics of the interface failure and matrix plasticity are still being actively pursued since understanding the failure mechanism is critical to

the understanding and improvement of the load-carrying capability of the composite in this orientation.

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Figure 2. Stress-strain curves and acoustic emissions for SCS-6 fiber (a), which is similar to that of SCS-6 SP, ACMF (b), SCS-0 (c), and AC1 (d). The behavior of the various composites is significantly different.

Figure 3. Micrographs of the fiber and interface in SCS-6 (a,b) (SEM), and ACMF (c,d) (optical) composites. The interface in SCS-6 appears normal in the wing section (a), but in the center section (b), a gap is present where the reaction products were located. In ACMF, the interface and fiber appear normal in the wing (c), but a large crack in the fiber and at the interface is present in the center section (d).